

REPORT:

A1.2.3: Documented example of the test protocol for leakage and burst pressure

Work package 1

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity A1.2.3 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written by:

Florestan OGHEARD

Thomas Schrøder DAUGBJERG

Kevin ROMIEU

Vania SILVERIO

CETIAT

DTI

CETIAT

INESC MN

florestan.ogheard@cetiat.fr

tsda@teknologisk.dk

kevin.romieu@cetiat.fr

vania.silverio@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

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1. Scope

This document describes the documented example performed at CETIAT to demonstrate the application of leakage and burst pressure test protocols developed under task A1.2.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.2.3 M21	Using input from A1.1.2, and based on results of stakeholder surveys from A2.1.2, A3.1.1, A4.1.1 and discussions with End-user Advisory Board (A5.1.1), CETIAT, with support from IPQ, DTI, INESC MN, CMI and BHT, will perform a documented example of the test protocol for leakage and burst pressure in flow control performance characteristics developed in A1.2.2. The documented example will be performed in laboratory of CETIAT.	CETIAT , IPQ, DTI, INESC MN, CMI, BHT

2. Introduction

To illustrate the leakage tests described in activity A1.2.2 report, CETIAT performed a leakage test when flowing liquid through a polymer microfluidic chip, described in the following sections. The leakage test includes:

- Visual inspection test
- Pressure decay test
- Flow rate measurement test

The following paragraphs describe the device under test, the test setup, and the realisation and results of the different tests performed.

3. Device under test

The device under test was a "Fluidic 157" straight channel chip with 8 parallel channels provided by Microfluidic ChipShop (Figure 1, see [1]), with the following characteristics:

- Material: Topas (Topas is a COC – cyclic olefin copolymer – resin)
- 8 parallel channels of 100 μm width, 100 μm depth, 18 mm length
- 75.5 mm by 25.5 mm microscope slide format
- Luer fluidic interface

Figure 1: schematic of the device under test [1]

For the tests, the microfluidic chip was mounted vertically as depicted in Figure 2, with a camera and backlight illumination in opposite sides of the chip.

Figure 2: device under test mounted in a vertical position during testing. The lens, which is attached to the camera, can be seen at the bottom right of the image. Backlight illumination is visible on the top left.

4. Test setup

The test setup used for the leakage test was mounted according to Figure 3. Here the pressure controller is connected to the circuit by 1/16" stainless steel pipes. The flow passes through a flow sensor (the thermal mass flow meter in Figure 4), a pressure sensor and enters the microfluidic chip. The microfluidic chip outlet is closed with a plug. The camera is positioned transversally to the flow (precisely at 90 deg), with backlight illumination for higher contrast between liquid and air.

Figure 3: schematic of the leakage test setup. (F) flow sensor, (P) pressure sensor, (O) outlet of the microfluidic chip under test

The test setup as described previously can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Images of the test setup. The camera lens attached to the camera indicated on the left image is shown in the image on the right together with the microfluidic chip mounted vertically.

The test setup used the following equipment:

- Pressure controller: Elveflow OB1 MkII, used for 0-200 mbar or 0-2000 mbar.
- F (Flow sensor): 2 thermal mass flow sensors have been used alternatively for the tests:
 - Bronkhorst LO1 - 1.5 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ full range. Readings acquired using the FlowPlot software.
 - Elveflow MFS 2 - 7 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ full range. Readings acquired using the ESI software.
- P (Pressure sensor): Elveflow MFP inline microfluidic pressure sensor, 16 bar full range. Readings acquired using the ESI software.
- Camera (for in-situ flow measurement): JAI SP-12000M-CXP4-F with full resolution of 4096 x 3072 px and maximum frame rate of 189 fps at full resolution. The images were acquired using StreamPix Software and the post processing for the measurement of the flow rate was done through an in-house Python script using an adapted image correlation method [2], [3]. This camera setup is part of the French nano-flow rate primary standard.

Additionally, a thermo-hygro-barometer ROTRONIC LOG-HC2-P1 / HC2-C05 was used to record temperature, humidity, and ambient pressure at the device location. All pipes used to make the fluidic connection between the different items of the setup, from the pressure controller to the device under test, were stainless steel 1/16" pipes.

At the inlet port of the device under test, a luer male to threaded Upchurch adapter (reference P-683-01), with an additional threaded female-female Upchurch elbow, has been used to connect the fluidic path to the device under test, as shown in the next Figure 5.

Figure 5: Left: adapter used to connect the fluidic setup to the device under test. Right: adapter connected to the top end of the 4th channel from the right on the microfluidic chip.

Before initiating the tests, the outlet of the device was closed using a Luer plug (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Left: Luer plugs used to close the outlet of the channel under test. Right: plug mounted on the lower end of the channel under test (the 4th channel from the right).

All instruments were calibrated on their full range, and by traceability to national standard at CETIAT laboratory or by ISO17025 accredited laboratories.

5. Visual inspection test

Using the test setup presented in the previous section, and after 30 min warming time after power on, the pressure has been set to increase by steps from 0 to 200 mbar (pressure at the outlet of the pressure controller). Figure 7 presents the pressure recorded at the pressure controller outlet up to 90000 ms period.

Figure 7: pressure increase at the inlet of the device under test during visual leakage test.

During this test, the device under test has been visually inspected for defects that could indicate leakage. Indeed, at 70 mbar the appearance of a leak was visually detected (Figure 8).

Figure 8: leak appearing at the device under test inlet during the visual leakage test.

6. Pressure decay test

Using the test setup presented in section 4, but using a different channel, the inlet pressure of the device under test has been increased and monitored from 0 to 1400 mbar in steps. At each step, the pressure was fixed at a given setpoint by the pressure controller for 3 minutes to detect possible pressure decay. For this documented example, the leakage detected by the pressure decay test occurred for 1400 mbar, as seen from the variability and subsequent decay in pressure in Figure 9.

Figure 9: a) inlet pressure of the device under test during the pressure decay leakage test.
 b) zoom on the pressure decay due to leakage around 1400 mbar.

7. Flow rate measurement test

Using the test setup presented in section 4 in yet another channel, the pressure has been increased by steps and the flow rate between the pressure controller and the device under test has been monitored over time using the thermal mass flow meter (Figure 10). The step in flow rate observed from 0 to 460 nL/min at around 4340 s indicates leakage flow for an imposed pressure of 1400 mbar.

Figure 10: inlet pressure and consequent flow rate step during leakage flow.

8. Summary

This documented example aimed at showing the application of leakage test to a microfluidic device. By using visual inspection, pressure decay and flow measurement tests, leakages in microfluidic channels were successfully detected.

9. References

- [1] Microfluidics ChipShop, Fluidic 157
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- [3] Metrology for Drug Delivery, REPORT: A1.2.5 : Calibration methods for measuring the response or delay time of drug delivery devices using Newtonian liquids for flow rates from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min
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